

QUESTIONNAIRE: INNOVATION PERFORMANCE OF SMEs IN VIETNAM

Dear Respondent,

This survey is part of a research project investigating the innovation ecosystem and performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam. As a key executive or R&D manager, your insights are highly valuable.

Anonymity & Confidentiality: Please be assured that all your responses will be kept strictly anonymous and confidential. The data collected will be used exclusively for academic research purposes and aggregated for statistical analysis. No individual firm or participant will be identified in any publication.

By proceeding to the next section, you voluntarily consent to participate in this study. Thank you for your time and contribution!

I. SECTION A: FIRM AND RESPONDENT PROFILE

Please tick () or mark (X) the most appropriate option in the boxes below.

1. Geographic Region	2. Industry Sector
<input type="checkbox"/> Hanoi (Northern Hub)	<input type="checkbox"/> High-tech Agriculture
<input type="checkbox"/> Da Nang (Central Hub)	<input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing & Industry
<input type="checkbox"/> Ho Chi Minh City (Southern Hub)	<input type="checkbox"/> Services (IT, Logistics, Finance)
3. Firm Size (Number of Personnel)	4. Your Current Position
<input type="checkbox"/> Micro & Small (< 50 employees)	<input type="checkbox"/> Board of Directors (CEO, VP, Chairman)
<input type="checkbox"/> Medium (50 - 200 employees)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D / Technology Manager
<input type="checkbox"/> Large (201 - 500 employees)	<input type="checkbox"/> Strategy / Planning Manager
<input type="checkbox"/> Very Large (> 500 employees)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Middle Manager

II. SECTION B: INSTITUTIONAL DRIVERS & NETWORKING *Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements regarding your firm's external environment. (Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)*

Code	Government Support (Resource Allocation)	1	2	3	4	5
GOV1	The government provides adequate financial incentives (tax breaks, preferential loans) for our innovation activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GOV2	We can easily access public infrastructure (high-tech parks, laboratories, incubation centers) necessary for our R&D.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GOV3	Government administrative procedures related to science and technology are clear and efficient.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GOV4	The legal framework for intellectual property protection effectively supports our innovation efforts.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GOV5	Information regarding state support programs for technology transfer is transparent and accessible.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Code	Intermediary Linkages (Triple Helix Interaction)	1	2	3	4	5
LINK1	We frequently collaborate with universities for training or recruitment of high-quality personnel.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
LINK2	We actively cooperate with public research institutes to solve technical problems or test new products.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
LINK3	We utilize services from technology brokers or innovation centers (e.g., NIC, local DOST centers).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
LINK4	We participate in industry associations to exchange market information and technological trends.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
LINK5	External partners play a crucial role in our decision-making process regarding new technology adoption.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

III. SECTION C: INTERNAL CAPABILITIES *Please indicate your level of agreement regarding your firm's internal capabilities and learning routines.*

Code	Internal R&D Readiness	1	2	3	4	5
RD1	Our company has a specific budget allocated annually for R&D and innovation activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
RD2	Our staff possesses the necessary technical skills and qualifications to conduct innovation projects.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
RD3	We have a dedicated department or team responsible for technology development and product improvement.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
RD4	We regularly organize training programs to update employees on new technological advancements.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Code	Absorptive Capacity (Dynamic Capability)	1	2	3	4	5
ACAP1	(Acquisition) Our company frequently scans the environment for new technologies and market trends.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ACAP2	(Assimilation) Our employees can quickly understand and analyze the potential value of new external information.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ACAP3	(Transformation) We serve as an effective bridge, combining new external knowledge with our existing internal processes.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ACAP4	(Exploitation) We are quick to commercialize new technical knowledge into products/services.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ACAP5	(Exploitation) We regularly use external knowledge to improve our existing product lines.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

IV. SECTION D: FIRM INNOVATION PERFORMANCE *Please indicate your level of agreement regarding your firm's innovation outputs over the last 3 years.*

Code	Firm Innovation Performance	1	2	3	4	5
PERF1	Compared to competitors, we have introduced a higher number of new products/services in the last 3 years.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
PERF2	The revenue share from new products/services has increased significantly.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
PERF3	We have significantly improved our operational processes to reduce costs or lead time.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
PERF4	Our new products/services effectively meet customer needs and enter new markets.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
PERF5	The overall technical quality of our products has improved significantly compared to the past.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Thank you for your valuable participation!